

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Xudoyberdiyeva Nargiza Tolibjon qizi

TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS THROUGH INTERACTIVE METHODS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/FEVRAL

